

THE REACTION BETWEEN MERCURY AND NITRIC ACID. A KINETIC STUDY

BY A. N. KAPPANNA AND K. M. JOSHI

When mercury is added to nitric acid, kept continuously stirred, in the range of concentrations of $4N$ to $7N$, the dissolution of the metal starts after an interval of time which may be designated the period of passivity. This period of passivity is greater in more dilute solutions than in more concentrated ones for a given rate of stirring.

The period of passivity in nitric acid solutions of a given concentration depends upon the rate of stirring, being greater in more rapidly stirred solutions.

The period of passivity is marked by the accumulation of nitrous acid in solution, until the concentration of nitrous acid at 22° reaches near about $0.0012N$ whereafter dissolution of mercury commences.

The period of passivity disappears if the nitric acid contains initially added nitrous acid in sufficient quantities.

After the period of passivity, the rate of dissolution is greater in more concentrated solutions than in less concentrated ones at a constant rate of stirring. In nitric acid solutions of the same concentration, the rate of dissolution slows down with increase in the rate of stirring.

A mechanism has been suggested for the dissolution of mercury in nitric acid. Nitrous acid is assumed to be the dissolving agent. The initial formation of nitrous acid is assumed to be due to the catalytic decomposition of nitric acid on the surface of mercury, the mercury surface forming an oxygen adsorption complex. The period of passivity has been explained as due to the retarding influence of nitric acid on the dissolving effect of nitrous acid and the period ending with the attainment of a critical concentration of nitrous acid in the reaction mixture.

Mercury belongs to that class of metals which do not ordinarily liberate hydrogen from nitric acid. The products formed in the reaction vary considerably with the conditions under which the reaction is allowed to take place. Literature on the subject is quite vast. From a kinetic viewpoint, however, the only extensive investigation on record is that of Veley (*Phil. Trans.*, 1891, **A**, 182, 279). Although it was known before, Veley showed conclusively that stirring of nitric acid in contact with mercury retarded the reaction. Veley further established that this retardation was due to the removal by stirring of the nitrous acid formed at the interface away from contact with the metal and that it was the initially formed nitrous acid that catalysed the dissolution of the metal. Hedges (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 561) studied the rate of dissolution of copper in nitric acid, and found the rate of dissolution to vary inversely with the rate of stirring and the attack of the metal by the acid could be prevented for quite a considerable length of time by increasing the stirring rate to 2000 r.p.m. Doubtless, similar data could be obtained with mercury in agitated nitric acid. It was the object of the present investigation to collect more information on the nature of the reaction between mercury and nitric acid. The points investigated relate to (1) whether and in what manner the period of passivity is dependent on the concentration of nitric acid and the rate of stirring, and (2) in what way does the rate of dissolution, when once dissolution commences, vary with the concentration of the acid and the rate of stirring.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The nitric acid used was of the guaranteed reagent quality. The stock acid showed the presence of nitrous acid. The removal of nitrous acid was effected by warming the acid to a temperature not exceeding 40° and agitating the acid by passing a stream of purified air. The passage of air was continued until tests (with an acetic acid solution of sulphanic acid and α -naphthylamine) proved the complete absence of nitrous acid. The acid was then cooled and diluted to the desired extent.

Chemically pure double-distilled mercury was further purified by first shaking the metal with a dilute solution of potassium cyanide and sodium peroxide and washing it with distilled water. It was next repeatedly allowed to flow in thin stream through a long column of dilute nitric acid in which a small quantity of mercurous nitrate had been dissolved, and thereafter washing it by thorough shaking with air-free distilled water a number of times. It was then stored in glass-stoppered bottles under air-free distilled water. Immediately before use, this mercury was again washed with air-free distilled water.

The reaction was studied in large-sized Jena glass beakers (10 cm. diameter and 1.5 litre capacity). All-glass stirrers, rotated by an electric motor with arrangements for regulating speed, were employed. These were fixed in a framework and the positions of beakers in all experiments were adjusted in such a way that the stirrers were always situated at the centres of the beakers and the bottom blades of the stirrers were at a constant height above the surface of mercury.

One litre of nitric acid solution of the desired concentration was taken in the beaker and stirring started. When the rate of stirring was adjusted and became steady, mercury (50 c.c.) was taken in a burette and run into the nitric acid solution, care being taken to see that the tip of the burette was well underneath the surface of the nitric acid solution to ensure that mercury did not stream through air before getting into the nitric acid. This precaution was found necessary, as we observed that mercury, allowed to come in contact with air freely before entering nitric acid solution, did not always give reproducible results. The reason for this probably is the varying nature of the laboratory atmosphere. By observing the aforementioned precaution, however, we were able always to obtain reproducible data.

Immediately after the addition of mercury, as well as at intervals later, 10 c.c. samples of nitric acid solution were pipetted out and tested for nitrous acid and mercury.

All the experiments detailed below were carried out at 22°.

Preliminary experiments, carried out with nitric acid solutions in the range of concentrations of 4*N* to 7*N*, show that, when mercury is added to nitric acid which is already being stirred :—

(i) There is an interval of time which may be termed "the period of passivity" when the metal does not go into solution in nitric acid. This period has a constant magnitude for a given concentration of the acid and a particular rate of stirring but it varies both with concentration and rate of stirring.

(ii) During the period of passivity, when no trace of mercury could be detected in the solution, nitrous acid is continuously formed.

(iii) At a particular stage, which is the end of the period of passivity, dissolution of mercury commences and when once it commences, goes into solution rapidly and with continuously increasing tempo.

(iv) Under the conditions of our experiments the entire quantity of mercury going into solution is present as mercurous mercury.

Period of Passivity

A set of experiments was carried out to determine the influence of the concentration of the acid and the rate of stirring on the period of inactivity. The end of this period was reckoned by noting the time after the start of the experiment, when the first trace of mercury was detected by spot reaction with *p*-dimethylaminobenzilidene-rhodamine.

Table I gives the results of these experiments.

TABLE I

Conc of acid (N)	...	6	6	6	7	5	5	5	4
Rate of stirring (r. p. m.)	400	650	1000	1000	250	400	650	250	
Period of passivity (min.)	8	15	70	15	45	90	150	300	

The period of passivity appears from the table to depend both on the rate of stirring and on the concentration of the acid.

Formation of Nitrous acid during the Period of Passivity

As mentioned above, nitrous acid is continuously formed during the period of passivity. Ten c.c. of the reacting nitric acid were withdrawn from the beaker at intervals, diluted with 40-50 c.c. of water and titrated against *N*/200-permanganate solution and the concentration of nitrous acid calculated from the titre. Table II gives the results of two experiments.

TABLE II

Conc. of HNO ₃ = 4.61N. Rate of stirring = 450 r. p. m.		Conc. of HNO ₃ = 5.0N. Rate of stirring = 600 r. p. m.	
Time after addition of mercury.	Conc. of nitrous acid in equiv. per litre.	Time after addition of mercury.	Conc. of nitrous acid in equiv. per litre.
0 min.	0	0 min.	0
88	0.00044	50	0.00024
120	0.00104	110	0.00090
135	0.00108	125	0.00124
153	0.00120		
After this, mercury was found in solution.		After this, mercury was found in solution.	

Experiments carried out with other concentrations of nitric acid and other rates of stirring show that under varied conditions, the dissolution of the metal commences invariably when the concentration of nitrous acid reaches a value between 0.0012*N* and 0.00125*N*.

Rate of Dissolution of Mercury after the Period of Passivity.—It has been stated earlier that when dissolution takes place under conditions when nitric acid is kept continuously stirred, the entire quantity of mercury going into solution does so in the mercurous state. Ten c. c. samples of the reaction solution were pipetted out at intervals after the period of passivity, diluted and the mercury was precipitated as mercurous chloride with all the necessary precautions. The precipitate was collected in Gooch crucibles, washed, dried below 90° and weighed. The amount of mercury per litre of solution was calculated from the weight of mercurous chloride. Tables III to VI contain the results of a few experiments.

TABLE III

Conc. of acid = 5*N*.
Rate of stirring = 500 r.p.m.
Period of passivity = 90 minutes.

Time after period of passivity.	Wt. of Hg /litre of solution.
3 min.	0.1197 g.
18	0.1535
48	0.4418
78	1.1088
108	3.5176

TABLE IV

Conc. of acid = 6*N*.
Rate of stirring = 400 r.p.m.
Period of passivity = 8 minutes

Time after period of passivity.	Wt. of Hg /litre of solution.
1 min.	0.4418 g
15	6.0631
28	8.5307
48	64.4900
63	126.0800

TABLE V

Conc. of acid = 6*N*. Rate of stirring = 650 r.p.m. Period of passivity = 15 minutes.

Time after period of passivity.	Wt. of Hg/litre of solution.
12 min.	2.9059 g.
25	8.0575
42	24.6921
53	43.1548
68	71.3378

TABLE VI

Conc. of acid = 6*N*. Rate of stirring = 1000 r.p.m. Period of passivity = 70 minutes.

Time after period of passivity.	Wt. of Hg/litre of solution.
15 min.	0.2209 g.
50	0.9177
80	4.3758
110	7.8000

In all these cases it can be seen that the rate of dissolution indicates the existence of autocatalytic action.

We have found by simultaneous estimation of nitrous acid that the amount of nitrous acid was at all times far in excess of the quantity of mercury in solution. These results have not been included here, because under the best conditions, we could not attach quantitative importance to these analyses on account of the fact that once dissolution starts, nitrous fumes are evolved in copious quantities and even where colorimetric methods were employed, we could not convince ourselves of the accuracy of our determinations.

Nevertheless, there appears little doubt that the quantity of nitrous acid is always, after the period of passivity, in large excess over the quantity corresponding to the formation of mercurous nitrite. We are mentioning this here as a plausible reason for the autocatalytic nature of the dissolution.

It will be observed from Tables III to VI that for a given concentration of acid, even as the period of passivity becomes greater with increase in the rate of stirring, the rate of dissolution falls very considerably with increase in the rate of stirring.

Influence of Initially added Mercurous Nitrate.—A few experiments were carried out to see if mercurous ion, initially present, would influence either the period of passivity or the rate of dissolution thereafter in any way. The results in all cases show that mercurous ion has no influence. We have not therefore included these results here.

Influence of Initially present Nitrous Acid on the Period of Passivity and Rate of Dissolution.—A standard solution of sodium nitrite, prepared from a purified sample of the salt, was added in different quantities to solutions of nitric acid (being stirred) before the addition of mercury and the effect studied. It is assumed that the concentration of the initially present nitrous acid is equal to the concentration of sodium nitrite. Tables VII to X contain a few of the results.

TABLE VII

Conc. of acid = 4*N*.
Rate of stirring = 450 r.p.m.
Initial conc. of HNO₂ = 0.00780*N*.
Period of passivity = Nil.

Time.	Wt. of Hg/litre of soln.
30 min.	0.06799 g.
45	0.0850
75	0.2549
140	0.5863
190	0.9346

TABLE VIII

Conc. of acid = 4*N*.
Rate of stirring = 450 r.p.m.
Initial conc. of HNO₂ = 0.0156*N*.
Period of passivity = Nil.

Time.	Wt of Hg/litre of soln.
30 min.	0.2379 g.
45	0.4263
75	0.5778
140	0.9686
190	1.3765

TABLE IX

Conc. of acid = 5*N*.
 Rate of stirring = 650 r.p.m.
 Initial conc. of $\text{HNO}_2 = 0.0039 \text{ } N$.
 Period of passivity = Nil.

Time.	Wt. of Hg /litre of soln.
15 min.	0.0339 g.
38	0.3229
54	0.7817
83	2.7800

TABLE X

Conc. of acid = 5*N*.
 Rate of stirring = 650 r.p.m.
 Initial conc. of $\text{HNO}_2 = 0.0078 \text{ } N$.
 Period of passivity = Nil.

Time.	Wt. of Hg/litre of soln.
5 min.	0.1605 g.
18	0.5693
38	1.5044
54	2.5575
83	4.7014

These results indicate clearly that the rate of dissolution definitely increases with increase in the initial concentration of nitrous acid. It will be noted that the initial concentration of nitrous acid in each of the cases above is much higher than the critical concentration of nitrous acid (spontaneously formed in contact with mercury) necessary to start dissolution. It is not surprising therefore that there is no period of passivity. We have carried out experiments with initial concentrations of nitrous acid slightly below and slightly above $0.0012 \text{ } N$. In cases where the initial concentration of nitrous acid was below $0.0012 \text{ } N$, a period of passivity was observed until the concentration of nitrous acid in solution reached round about this value before dissolution started. We chose 4*N* solutions of nitric acid for these experiments as the period of passivity in this solution even at the low rate of stirring of 250 r. p. m. was as high as 5 hours, and any differences that altered conditions might create would be more pronounced. Tables VII and VIII show unmistakably the effect of initial addition of nitrous acid.

DISCUSSION

In arriving at or suggesting any particular mechanism for the reaction between nitric acid and mercury or any other metal, it is necessary to confine ourselves to the particular condition of the experiments in which the nitric acid is kept continuously stirred before the metal is brought in contact with acid. In the case of copper, Hedges (*loc. cit.*) has observed the formation of a visible oxide film on the surface and therefore the dissolution of the metal in nitric acid or nitrous acid, as may be the case, is suggested to be through the formation of this oxide. This may be a correct mechanism for copper. We have tried to make careful observations in our experiments during the period of passivity, and we have not been able to observe any change in the appearance of mercury surface in contact with agitated nitric acid during this period. In any case, we have no grounds to infer that a visible oxide film, which is in any way distinguishable from the mercury surface itself, is formed before dissolution starts. The initial formation of nitrous acid from nitric acid and its accumulation up to a definite concentration before dissolution of mercury starts, remains a fact that should

be explained, in our opinion, on a slightly different basis. To suggest that nitrous acid is formed by the catalytic decomposition of nitric acid on mercury surface without either any visible evolution of oxygen or the formation of an oxide, would call for a mechanism something akin to the formation of an adsorbed oxygen layer on the surface of mercury. The question would then be how does the oxygen layer help in starting dissolution? Does it help at all, and if so, in what way? It is pertinent here to recall the results of Veley (*loc. cit.*) where he proves that nitrous acid dissolves mercury quite readily and the influence of nitric acid on this reaction is to retard the dissolution. One has to conclude therefore that in the reaction between mercury and nitric acid, nitric acid as such does not react with and dissolve mercury at all, particularly under the conditions of the experiments carried out in the present investigation, but the cause of the dissolution of mercury is the nitrous acid formed initially, as we have suggested here, by catalytic decomposition at the surface of mercury. This view is further substantiated by our observation that nitrous acid formation oversteps in rate the dissolution of mercury, after the period of passivity. We would therefore suggest the following mechanism:—

The reactions involving the formation of nitrous acid are assumed to predominate in rates over the reactions involving the disappearance of the acid.

Period of Passivity.—It now remains to explain the cause for the period of passivity and its variation with the rate of stirring. Nitrous acid happens to be the dissolving agent. Why then does it accumulate up to a concentration of about 0.0012N in the nitric acid solution before it acts upon mercury? Here again we have to draw support from the experiments of Veley relating to the retarding influence of nitric acid on the dissolving effect of nitrous acid.

While nitrous acid is capable of dissolving mercury, it would not be correct to assume that the heterogeneous reaction is either rapid or as one not involving large energy of activation. At very low concentrations of nitrous acid, as in the initial stages of its formation, the rate of reaction is unnoticeable. Added to this we have to take note of the fact that nitric acid present in large quantities has great retarding effect on this reaction and this retarding effect would be rather highly pronounced when only traces of nitrous acid happen to be present. Under these opposing forces tending

towards retarding the dissolution, however, a stage must be reached when the retarding effect should be just overcome by the increasing concentration of nitrous acid; and this stage appears to be reached near about the concentration of 0.0012*N* at the temperature at which we have carried out the experiments.

Our observations, as stated earlier, lead to the conclusion that the rate of formation of nitrous acid at the surface of mercury is itself an autocatalytic reaction, and the rapidity with which the nitrous acid formed at the surface could be removed therefrom would determine the rate of accumulation of nitrous acid in the bulk of solution *i. e.* if the rate of stirring is increased, the rate of formation of nitrous acid at the surface is naturally diminished. Hence, the delay in the nitrous acid concentration attaining the required critical value when rate of stirring is increased. The increase in the period of passivity with increase in the rate of stirring thus becomes understandable.

The mechanism and the explanation suggested above pertain mostly to the reactions leading to the commencement of dissolution. Once dissolution commences, the formation of oxides of nitrogen further complicates the processes. The surface reactions including dissolution of mercury still appear to be determined and dominated by the period of contact of the products with the surface and with increased rates of stirring, we observe, for the same concentration of acid, the rate of dissolution falls as shown in the following table.

TABLE XI

Conc. of acid.	Revolutions per minute.	Passivity period.	Amount of Hg dissolved in about the same time after passivity.
6 <i>N</i>	400	8 mins.	64.49 g. (48 mins.)
6	650	15	43.1548 g. (53 ,,)
6	1000	70	0.9177 g. (50 ,,)

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
COLLEGE OF SCIENCE, NAGPUR.

Received June 5, 1948.